

Free vibration analysis of erythrocytes using the constant strain finite elements: a 3D study

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Abstract

Red blood cells (RBCs), also called erythrocytes, represent an important component of blood and are responsible for one of its main functions, the transport of oxygen to the entire body, which is essential for human life. As other cells of the human body, associated with a specific pathology, RBCs can present their properties and features changed in a singular way. For instance, changes in the cell geometry lead to a distinct mechanical response. Usually, each body possesses a specific natural vibration frequency, which is associated with its geometry, stiffness and mass. This characteristic allows to develop new treatments and forms of diagnosis by targeting pathologic cells possessing a natural vibration frequency different from the healthy ones. Thus, the objective of this work is to analyse the behaviour of RBCs, both normal and with well-known pathologies, using the finite element method (FEM). For this, 3D models were constructed and free vibration simulations were performed. The first four vibration modes of the different types of RBCs were qualitatively analysed. Potential fields were constructed based on the vibration modes obtained with the FEM analysis, such as potential displacement field and stress potential fields. The simulation was performed resorting to constant strain finite elements. In the end, as expected, it was possible to conclude that alterations in the initial geometry of RBCs imply significant changes in the cell mechanical response.

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1. Introduction

RBCs present a simple biological structure, without nucleus or cellular organelles, and their cytoplasm is made up of 95% haemoglobin. Due to this last property, RBCs are responsible for taking oxygen to and from the tissues, which is one of the most important functions in the human body [1]. Their mechanical properties, integrity, and biological functions are dependent on the cellular membrane and their elastic protein network is responsible for their shear elastic properties [2, 3].

As other cells, RBCs can present changes in their mechanical properties, specially, in their deformability, due to some pathologies. Some examples of pathologies that affect RBCs are sickle cell anaemia, spherocytosis, or malaria. All of these represent a major problem and challenge for the medical field since they are associated with a large number of deaths, every year [4, 5]. In order to overcome these problems, several attempts have been made to understand the behaviour of normal and pathological RBCs. In the computational biomechanics field, several numerical simulations have been made and, currently, they are considered as a powerful tool to perform different types of analyses [6, 7].

Regarding the natural vibration frequency, due to its geometry and material properties, all bodies possess unique vibration frequencies and vibration modes. Such structural signature can be modified if the structure changes its geometry or its stiffness or its mass [8]. For instance, under some pathologies, RBCs modify their geometry and, therefore, change their vibration response. It is expected to capture such changes resorting to biomechanical simulations. Note that, this modification in the natural frequency of vibration of RBCs has not yet been completely understood.

In the biomechanical simulations field, several methods are currently used to analyse RBCs. From these, it is possible to highlight the Finite Element Method (FEM) [9, 10] or the Dissipative Particle Dynamics (DPD) method [11, 12]. Also, 2D models are usually used to perform the analyses, since they are simple, present low computation costs, and are often sufficient to obtain a suitable approximation. Regarding research works using this type of models, some examples are

presented in [13] and [14]. However, it is important to stress that RBCs are 3D structures so, to obtain more realistic analyses, 3D models should be considered, and some examples are already presented in [15] and [16].

Thus, the objective of the present work is to qualitatively analyse normal and pathological RBCs models, in terms of natural vibration frequency, and potential von Mises effective stress profiles. For such purpose, three distinct forms of RBCs were created (one healthy normal RBCs and two abnormal RBCs related to ovalocytosis and sickle cell anaemia), and analysed in FEMAS® (Finite Element and Meshless Analysis Software), a freeware academic software (cmech.webs.com), using 3D constant strain finite elements.

2. Finite Element Method

Emerged in the 1950's, the FEM is the most popular mesh-dependent method. However, it was only used in biomechanics for the first time in 1972 [17, 18]. This method is currently a powerful numerical tool that allows the resolution of a large and complex system of equations, being an effective tool to modulate systems in a wide range of fields [17, 19]. As other discretization techniques, the domain is divided in partitions, and each partition is linked to the other partitions of the domain by shared borders, which allows the formation of a mesh [20]. In the case of the FEM, the domain is discretized in finite elements that are connected by nodes, with a pre-establish configuration, which allows to form a mesh [21]. From these elements, linear functions, known as shape functions, are constructed and the approximated distribution of the variable under study is obtained, in order to establish the equations that allow to find the global system of equations [18]. By solving the global system of equations, the field variables are obtained, acquiring an approximate solution [21, 22]. Note that, the number of nodes and elements, the geometry of the problem, the mesh configuration and boundary conditions affect the computational time of the analysis and the accuracy of the obtained results [22]. Regarding the advantages of the FEM, it presents a simple discretization concept, a low computational cost, and results possessing a satisfactory degree of accuracy. Furthermore, FEM is easy to program and allows to analyse irregular surfaces easily. Besides this, it is possible to combine different materials and boundary conditions in the same body [17, 23]. However, in large deformation problems, the distortion of the mesh decreases the accuracy and the stability of the results [17].

3. Discrete system of equations

If a structure is exposed to loads/forces, it becomes stressed and, thus, strained, which can be understood as deformations or relative displacements. However, to analyse a deformation, alterations in the configuration of the body should be considered and this is usually expressed in terms of stress and strain, which allows to define the virtual work as the integral over the body volume [24]. Thus, the stress tensor can be defined as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \{ \sigma_{xx} \quad \sigma_{yy} \quad \sigma_{xy} \}^T \quad (1)$$

and the strain tensor as:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \{ \varepsilon_{xx} \quad \varepsilon_{yy} \quad \varepsilon_{xy} \}^T \quad (2)$$

Regarding these two variables, it is possible to define them as: $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{u}$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{c}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, with $\mathbf{c}$ as the material constitutive matrix. Resorting to the Galerkin weak form, it is possible to obtain the discrete equation system. With this, the solution that allows to obtain the more accurate configuration, in terms of displacements, is the one that minimizes the Lagrangian functional (L), which is defined as:

$$L = T - U + W_f \quad (3)$$

where T represents the kinetic energy, U the strain energy and W_f the work performed by the external forces, which can be defined, respectively, as:

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \rho \dot{\mathbf{u}}^T \dot{\mathbf{u}} d\Omega$$

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} d\Omega \quad (4)$$

$$W_f = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{b} d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_t} \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{t} d\Gamma_t$$

Note that, $\dot{\mathbf{u}}$ is the velocity, and ρ the density of the solid. If the functional is integrated with respect to time and then minimized, following the principle of virtual work and assuming the relations $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{c}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{u}$, four equation terms will be obtained [24]:

$$\delta \mathbf{u}_S^T \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{H}_I^T \boldsymbol{\rho} \mathbf{H}_I d\Omega}_{\mathbf{M}} \ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \delta \mathbf{u}_S^T \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}_I^T \mathbf{c} \mathbf{B}_I d\Omega}_{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{u} - \delta \mathbf{u}_S^T \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{H}_I^T \mathbf{b} d\Omega}_{\mathbf{f}_b} - \delta \mathbf{u}_S^T \underbrace{\int_{\Gamma_t} \mathbf{H}_I^T \bar{\mathbf{t}} d\Gamma_t}_{\mathbf{f}_t} = 0 \quad (5)$$

with $\mathbf{B}_I$ as the deformability matrix, $\mathbf{H}_I$ is the diagonal matrix containing the shape functions, $\mathbf{b}$ is the body force vector actuating in the solid domain Ω and $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$ is the traction force vector actuating in the domain boundary Γ_t .

In the end, the equilibrium equation is found and defined as:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{F} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{K}$ represents the stiffness matrix, $\mathbf{M}$ is the mass matrix, $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}$ and $\mathbf{u}$ are the acceleration and displacement field, respectively, and $\mathbf{F}$ the vector of forces that include both the body weight vector ($\mathbf{f}_b$) and the external forces vector ($\mathbf{f}_t$). Following the demonstration shown in [24], in order to obtain the vibration modes and vibration frequencies, it is necessary to neglect the applied forces, $\mathbf{F}$, and solve the following equation,

$$\det(\mathbf{K} - \omega^2 \mathbf{M}) \boldsymbol{\Phi} = \mathbf{0} \quad (7)$$

The solution will provide $3N$ vibration frequencies ω , being N the number of nodes discretizing the problem domain, and $3N$ vectors $\boldsymbol{\Phi}$ with size $[3N \times 1]$ representing the vibration modes. The first vibration mode, corresponding to the lowest energy mode, is known as natural frequency and its corresponding vibration mode is its natural vibration mode. The vibration frequencies and their corresponding vibration modes are the Eigen-values and Eigen-vectors of equation (2).

4. Numerical Results

For the present work, three different 3D geometries of RBCs were created, one presenting a normal healthy RBC (H), and the other two representing a RBC affected by sickle cell anaemia (SCA) and ovalocytosis (also known as hereditary elliptocytosis) (O). Note that, all models were created following realistic geometries (an average diameter of $7.5\mu\text{m}$), based on data presented in the literature [25] and a representation of each one is presented next. Moreover, the mechanical properties (Young's modulus and Poisson's coefficient [25]) used for each model are presented in Table 1. All the cells possess the same density: $1.110 \times 10^{-9} \text{kg}/\mu\text{m}^3$.

Fig.4 –The three models used, where H represents the healthy RBC, SC a cell affected by sickle cell anaemia and O by ovalocytosis.

Table 1 –Values of Young’s modulus and Poisson coefficient for the three different cases [25].

RBC	Young’s Modulus (N/μm ²)	Poisson’s Coefficient
H	2,6×10 ⁻⁸	0,499
SCA	3,7143×10 ⁻⁸	0,45
O	8,423×10 ⁻⁸	0,45

The analyses of the first four modes of vibration were performed in FEMAS®, for each case, and it was imposed that cells can vibrate freely, i.e., no degree of freedom was constrained. The results obtained are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Analysing the results presented in Table 2, it is possible to visualise that different geometries of RBCs led to different values of vibration frequency, as expected. Besides that, it is also possible to visualise that each vibration frequency is associated with a vibration mode (deformed shape of the RBCs). Such vibration mode corresponds to the potential deformation that the RBC will experience when excited with the corresponding vibration frequency. Thus, low vibration frequencies (low energy frequencies) induce simpler vibration modes, and higher vibration frequencies correspond to more complex vibration modes shapes. In the results, it is also possible to note that the final vibration modes shapes of the H and O models are similar since the initial models also present comparable geometries. However, since they are not equal, the vibration frequencies are different, as expected.

Notice that the models can vibrate by resonance if a vibration frequency is externally induced (an ultra-sound source, for instance). Thus, the lowest vibration frequency is always the first to be identified by resonance, corresponding to the lowest energy vibration frequency (this first vibration frequency is known as natural frequency). As expected, the results show that low energy vibration frequencies are associated with simple vibration modes and as the model’s vibration frequency increases, the vibration mode becomes more complex. This observation is valid for all presented figures.

Despite the model under analysis (H, SCA or O), notice that the results show that the first vibration frequency is always very different from the other vibration frequencies. This allows to clearly identify the natural vibration mode, by a comfortable large margin, allowing to suggest a value for potential therapies or diagnostics.

Table 2 - Colour map of the first four free vibration modes and corresponding vibration frequencies ($\hat{\omega}_{1,2,3 \text{ and } 4}$) obtained with FEM.

Assuming the i^{th} vibration mode as potential displacement fields, $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i = \Phi_i$, it is possible to obtain the corresponding stress field, $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_i = \mathbf{c}\bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_i$. With this field, it is possible to establish the von Mises effective stress field, $\bar{\sigma}_i$,

$$\bar{\sigma}_i = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \left(\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_i - \frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_i) \mathbf{I} \right) : \left(\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_i - \frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_i) \mathbf{I} \right)} \quad (8)$$

The results shown in Table 3 are only qualitative results. The magnitude $\bar{\sigma}_i$ is not relevant, because it was obtained for a potential (fictitious) displacement field, $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i$. Nevertheless, it is possible to visualize and analyse the locations in which higher levels of the von Mises effective stress field, $\bar{\sigma}_i$, will occur in the RBCs. Therefore, the distributions shown in Table 3 represent this field. For the H-RBCs, the first vibration mode induces higher stress values near the border of the RBC. In contrast, for the SCA-RBCs and the O-RBC, the corresponding first vibration mode leads to higher stress values in the centre of the RBC. Concerning the O-RBC, this result was not expected. Observing Table 2, the first vibration modes of the H-RBCs and O-RBC are very similar. Thus, expectedly these two cells should present a similar stress field. Such results indicate that sub-surface deformations are occurring inside the RBC that influence significantly the final stress fields. These results are relevant since they provide the locations of the RBC in which the stress field shows higher values in a resonance scenario, indicating the potential rupture sites of the RBC.

Table 3 - Colour map of the von Mises effective stress fields $\bar{\sigma}_i$ of the first four free vibration modes ($\hat{\omega}_{1,2,3 \text{ and } 4}$) obtained with FEM.

5. Conclusion

Diseases related to RBCs affect a large number of people, representing a severe impact on the quality of life of the patients and also on the economy, due to the high cost associated to them. As in other cells, different pathologies can influence the natural structure and the properties of the RBCs in different ways. This way, the use of numerical simulations can be useful to understand and overcome diseases related to these cells. Thus, the objective of the present work was to qualitatively analyse the first four modes of vibration of the RBCs. For this, a constant strain 3D FEM was

used and three 3D models (one representing a normal RBC, and another two representing two specific diseases related to RBC, the sickle cell anaemia and ovalocytosis) were constructed and analysed.

Regarding the natural frequencies obtained for each geometry, this study allows to predict the following natural frequencies for each RBC: $\hat{\omega}_1^H = 1.715\text{rad/s}$, $\hat{\omega}_1^{SCA} = 0.777\text{rad/s}$ and $\hat{\omega}_1^O = 2.494\text{rad/s}$. As it is possible to verify, each kind of geometry possesses a unique and very distinct natural frequency. Thus, in the future, using this knowledge, it will be possible to design diagnosis procedures capable to identify the fraction of pathological RBCs per volume using ultrasonic techniques. More, if the aim is to eliminate pathologic RBCs, the ultrasonic technique can be used to excite blood volumes with the same frequency as the natural frequency of the pathological RBC and induce resonance. The resonance will lead to the collapse of the pathologic RBC following the red areas represented in Table 3, leaving the healthy RBCs and other cell and structures unharmed. This technique is already used in kidney stone treatment by shock wave (high-energy sound waves).

This study presents some limitations, as for instance, the low number of nodes used in the discretization, which might influence the accuracy of the final results, and the lack of involving material (fluid). This way, in the future, these parameters should be improved, and convergence tests must be done to obtain the ideal values for each model.

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